

Pyridine chemistry from Chichibabin's reactions to metal catalysed C-H functionalizations – An overview[†]

Eric F. V. Scriven^{a*} and Ramiah Murugan^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Florida, Gainesville, FL 32611, USA

E-mail : Efvsl@aol.com

^bVertellus Specialties Inc, Indianapolis, IN 46242, USA

E-mail : murugan@vertellus.com

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Abstract : A short overview of some new pyridine reactions contrasted with older ones in commercial use is presented.

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Introduction

The pyridine ring is an integral part of many of the most important and highest volume bioactive entities available today, for example, niacin (1) and niacinamide (2) (human and animal health)¹, paraquat (3) (herbicide)², imidacloprid (4) (insecticide) (Fig. 1)³.

Fig. 1

Pyridine and the picolines (2-, 3- and 4-methylpyridines) were obtained on an industrial scale from distillation of the basic fraction of coal tar. When addition

of 2-vinylpyridine (obtained from 2-methylpyridine) to butadiene-styrene latex was found to increase the adhesion of rubber to tire cord, the demand for 2-methylpyridine increased dramatically. This began to exceed its availability from coal tar distillation. So a vapor phase catalytic process originally discovered by Chichibabin (1905)⁴ was developed and introduced in the early 1950's. This process involves passing acetaldehyde and ammonia over a catalyst at a high temperature to give a mixture of 2- and 4-picolines (Scheme 1). A similar process (Scheme 1) for converting acetaldehyde, formaldehyde and ammonia into pyridine and 3-picoline was developed to meet the increase in demand for these two products⁵.

Four streams of major pyridine (final or intermediate) products (Scheme 1) originate from these two co-product processes to serve a 150,000 MTY marketplace.

The opportunities described above have driven intensive studies of the synthesis and reactivity of pyridines which still continue. The enabling reactions involved in the pathways illustrated (Scheme 2) are :

Ammoxidation – picolines into cyanopyridines.

Chichibabin amination – pyridine and methylpyridines into 2-aminopyridines.

Hofmann reaction – 3- and 4-cyanopyridines into 3- and 4-aminopyridines.

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Catalytic reduction – pyridine and picolines into corresponding piperidines.

Condensation reactions – 2- and 4-picolines into corresponding vinylpyridines.

Cyanopyridines

Cyanopyridines are available for many direct high yield conversions illustrated below (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

The cyano group has been exploited as a leaving group in 2- and 4-cyanopyridines to give 2- and 4-substituted pyridines, respectively. For example, 4-pyridylcarbinols have been made using this approach by reacting 4-cyanopyridine with aromatic ketones in the presence of sodium metal (Scheme 4)⁶. Anions generated from α,α -

Scheme 4

disubstituted esters or nitriles readily displace the cyano group at the 2- and 4-positions of the pyridine ring by a nucleophilic substitution process (Scheme 5)⁷.

Aminopyridines

The first high yield direct synthesis of aminopyridines

was reported by Chichibabin in 1914⁸. He intended to metallate the methyl group in 2-picoline by treating it with sodamide at reflux in toluene, instead he obtained 2-amino-6-methylpyridine. Aminopyridines⁹ have found great utility in the synthesis of a number of active pharmaceutical compounds (Fig. 2).

A recent publication on a copper-mediated Sandmeyer reaction has shown that the amino group in aminopyridines could be replaced by a trifluoromethyl group. The reagent used is *S*-trifluoromethyldibenzothiophenium tetrafluoroborate along with copper and alkyl nitrite under mild reaction conditions (Scheme 6)¹⁰.

Methylpyridines

Methyl groups attached at the 2- and 4-positions of the pyridine ring undergo condensation reactions analogous to those of a methyl substituent α to a carbonyl group¹¹. 2- and 4-Vinylpyridines are produced commercially in this way (Scheme 7).

Chloropyridines

Chlorination at a ring position is a difficult reaction in the pyridine series compared with benzene analogues, unless at least one activating group is present in the ring (for example, amino). Symmetrical tetrachloropyridine (symtet) is a key intermediate in the synthesis of the herbicide chlorpyrifos¹². Symtet is prepared by a “deep chlorination” which results in the formation of mono-, several di- and tri-chloropyridines as byproducts, which are available commercially (Scheme 8). Chlorination of pyri-

Scheme 5

Sulfasalazine

Nalidixic acid

Zolpidem

Nevirapine

Fig. 2

Scheme 6

Scheme 7

Chlorpyrifos

Scheme 8

dine and picolines, specifically α - and β -picolines, has been done both under liquid phase (temperatures below 200 °C) as well as vapor phase (temperatures above 250 °C) conditions, and as mentioned above, symtet and

pentachlorinated pyridine are the thermodynamic sink products¹³.

Pyridine *N*-oxides

Pyridine *N*-oxides can be prepared under fairly mild conditions unless several electron-withdrawing groups are attached to the ring (Scheme 9). Pyridine *N*-oxides can be nitrated fairly easily to afford 4-nitropyridine (Scheme 9), more forcing conditions are required if electron-withdrawing groups are present. The chlorination of 3-pyridine carboxylic acid *N*-oxide with phosphorus oxychloride

Scheme 9

ride is practiced commercially and it gives a high yield of the 2-chloro-3-pyridine carboxylic acid after workup, very little of the 6-isomer is found (Scheme 9). 2-Chloro-3-pyridine carboxylic acid is used to make several commercial products, for instance the herbicides Diflufenican and Nicosulfuron¹⁴ (Fig. 3). Competition between ring and substituent reactions have been found in some other chlorination and especially in acetylations¹⁵.

Fig. 3

It is clear from the above that pyridines differ from corresponding benzenoid compounds in their reactivity. Until recently, synthetic considerations when embarking on a synthesis involving a pyridine compared with benzenoid compound have been rather different. The development of directed *ortho* metallation (*D-o-M*), cross-coupling reactions and metal-catalyzed C–H activation in benzenoid chemistry has been applied rapidly to pyridines with great success. The second part of this short overview will illustrate the applications and potential importance of some of these reactions.

Metallations using lithium

Direct lithiation of the pyridine ring occurs at the α -position¹⁶. Directed *ortho*-lithiation can occur in any position of the pyridine ring, depending on the nature and position of the directing group (DG) which could be amides, carbamates, alkoxy, amines, halogen, etc.¹⁷. Lithiation has also been achieved by metal halogen exchange on halogenated pyridines (Scheme 10)¹⁸. General schemes of directed lithiation on various substituted pyridines to make variously multisubstituted pyridine derivatives are given in Scheme 11.

Scheme 10

3-Halopyridines¹⁹ (Scheme 12), and 4-amino, -alkoxy, and -cyanopyridines²⁰ (Scheme 11) provide various 3,4-disubstituted pyridines on lithiation, followed by treatment with an electrophile. A 3-halopyridine with an oxazolidine group at the 5-position gives the expected directed lithiation at the 4-position with LDA, whereas with a much more hindered lithiating agent such as LTMP lithiation occurs at the 2-position²¹ in spite of the pres-

Scheme 11

Scheme 12

Scheme 13

Scheme 14

ence of a directing oxazolidine group at the 5-position (Scheme 13).

The synthesis of 2-substituted 3-pyridinols may be achieved by sequential metallations of OSEM-protected 3-pyridinol, followed by a desilylation of the trimethylsilyl group with TBAF (Scheme 14)²².

Lithiation studies of some halopyridines have revealed a rearrangement occurring via metal halogen exchange, referred to as halogen-dance. For example, in the synthesis of NK₁ antagonists, this halogen-dance methodology has been used as shown in Scheme 15. 2-Chloro-3-iodopyridine on metallation with LDA and quenching with the electrophile carbon dioxide gave 2-chloro-4-iodonicotinic acid, which on further transformation was converted into the final product the NK₁ antagonist²³.

The following examples describe synthetic applications of lithiated pyridines. For example, the synthesis of

Scheme 15

azaacridone A starting from 3-aminopyridine via directed metallation approach is shown (Scheme 16)²⁴.

Scheme 16

The formation of 3,4-pyridyne and its capture using furan, starting from 3-chloropyridine²⁵, is shown in Scheme 17.

Applications of cross-coupling reactions

Halopyridines and pyridine boronic esters have been used very effectively in palladium-catalyzed cross-coupling reactions of Suzuki, Stille, Heck, Negishi,

Sonogashira, Kumada, and Hiyama type to make a new C-pyridine bond²⁶. The Buchwald-Hartwig amination reaction²⁷ offers a superior method for formation of a N-pyridine bond. Synthesis of (*S*)-brevicolline starting from (*S*)-nicotine (Scheme 18), where a combination of lithiations, Suzuki coupling and Buchwald-Hartwig type amination has been used²⁸.

Synthesis of pyridine-fused thiophenes starting from 3-methylthiopyridine may be achieved by using Sonogashira coupling (Scheme 19)²⁹.

A 2,4-diarylpyridine has been synthesized starting from 2-bromopyridine by application of the use of halogen dance along with a Kumada cross-coupling reaction (Scheme 20). Preparation of 2-bromo-4-iodopyridine from 2-bromopyridine involves a halogen dance rearrangement. Conversion of this mixed dihalide to the final product under Kumada conditions exploits the difference in reactivity of the iodo and bromo substituents to introduce two different aryl groups at the 2- and 4-positions³⁰.

C-H Activation at substituents

Transition metal-catalyzed C-H activation in general is currently an area of intensive study. Specifically, C-H activation leading to functionalization of a phenyl ring attached at the 2-position of the pyridine ring is a new application in pyridine methodology. C-H functionalization avoids the prefunctionalization of coupling partners required for metal-catalyzed cross coupling. Various metal-

Scheme 17

Scheme 18

Scheme 19

catalysts have been used, e.g. palladium³¹, copper³², ruthenium³³, rhodium³⁴ and iron³⁵. New bonds formed by this method include C-C, C-Hal, C-O and C-N. Two examples are given below. The first utilizes a catalytic amount of palladium acetate (1–6 mol%) and 1.6 eq of $\text{PhI}(\text{OAc})_2$ to give 52% yield of the *o*-monoacetoxy prod-

uct (Scheme 21)³⁶. When the reaction is run in excess of 2 eq of $\text{PhI}(\text{OAc})_2$, the diacetoxy product is formed in 78% yield. The second example involves the amidation of 2-phenylpyridine with different nitrogen reagents, copper acetate (20 mol%) and oxygen as the terminal oxidant (Scheme 22)³².

Scheme 20

Scheme 21

Preferential oxidation at the benzylic CH₂ rather than at the methyl group has been achieved with an iron-catalyzed oxidation that employs oxygen. In contrast, copper-catalyzed oxidation results in oxidation of both substituents (Scheme 23)³⁵. The nature of the products formed is temperature dependent in these reactions.

Pyridine 2-benzylic amines undergo arylation using arylboronates with ruthenium(0)-sp³ C-H bond activation. It should be noted that a sterically demanding 3-substituent (methyl or phenyl) is critical for obtaining high yields (Scheme 24)³⁷.

Direct pyridine ring functionalization, namely arylation

Scheme 22

Scheme 23

Scheme 24

Scheme 25

of 2-picoline by rhodium-catalyzed C-H activation has been described (Scheme 25)³⁸.

The examples of C-H activation described above illustrate the advantage of eliminating several steps, for example, halogenation and formation of a boronic ester before palladium-cross coupling, and the possibility to move away from the use of toxic heavy metals. Approaches based on C-H activation hold great promise for the future in industrial synthetic pyridine chemistry³⁹. This short review has aimed to give a brief overview of advances in pyridine chemistry over the last 100 years and prospects for its future.

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